

Research Article

Bio-Based Corrosion Defense: Exploring Domestic Waste for Sustainable Steel Protection

Hazriel Faizal Pahroraji¹, Siti Khadijah Alias^{2*}, Haryana Mohd Hairi³, Mohd Alfatihhi Mohd Szali Januddi⁴, Bulan Abdullah⁵ and Masalina Md Ali⁶

¹ Universiti Teknologi MARA; hazriel@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5291-0482>)

² Universiti Teknologi MARA; khadijah_alias@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7410-9266>)

³ Universiti Teknologi MARA; haryana.hairi@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1320-6107>)

⁴ Universiti Kuala Lumpur; mohdalfatihhi@unikl.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7905-1913>)

⁵ Universiti Teknologi MARA; bulan_abd@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5802-6284>)

⁶ Universiti Kuala Lumpur; masalina@unikl.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9530-1495>)

* Correspondence: khadijah_alias@uitm.edu.my; +60123480423

Abstract: Significant attention to the presence of corrosion control during both the design and operational phases, including efforts in corrosion monitoring. Domestic waste has shown potential as an ecological corrosion inhibitor for carbon steel when exposed to 1 M Hydrochloric acid solution. Various concentrations of the waste were tested on carbon steel in an acidic environment through weight loss measurements over 7, 14, and 21 days. The results indicated that higher concentrations enhanced the corrosion resistance of the steel, with a maximum inhibition efficiency of 98.28%. In conclusion, domestic waste is an effective natural corrosion inhibitor that helps protect the steel surface and minimizes corrosion in carbon steel.

Keywords: Corrosion inhibitor; steel; weight loss.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Corrosion represents a significant degradation of carbon steel surfaces, particularly under acidic and alkaline conditions, such as those encountered in oil and gas pipelines, boilers, and structural components. This deterioration can result in equipment malfunction, reduced performance, diminished flexural capacity, and impaired surface bonding (Arthur & Abechi, 2019).

Various strategies have been employed to mitigate corrosion, including alloying, reducing metallic impurities, surface coatings, and cathodic protection. More recently, corrosion inhibitors have emerged as an attractive approach due to their simplicity and cost-effectiveness. Corrosion inhibitors function by forming a protective barrier on metal surfaces, thereby impeding electrochemical reactions; they are typically classified as cathodic, anodic, or mixed-type inhibitors based on their mechanism of action, involving alterations in oxidation energy (Bijapur et al., 2023).

Nonetheless, the widespread use of conventional corrosion inhibitors, often synthesized from toxic and hazardous materials, poses considerable risks to human health and the environment. Previous studies have demonstrated that prolonged exposure to inorganic inhibitors can have harmful

effects on humans, be toxic to plants and animals, and negatively impact environmental systems, including both surface and groundwater quality (Sunardi et al., 2023).

Given these concerns, the development of environmentally benign, naturally derived corrosion inhibitors is imperative to reduce the adverse impacts associated with traditional chemical inhibitors. The implementation of reliable toxicity assessment methods is also critical for the rational design of safer alternatives. Consequently, there has been growing research interest in exploring natural substances, such as plant extracts, flowers, leaves, fruits, and peels, as sustainable sources of corrosion inhibitors (Ayoola et al., 2022; Eddy et al., 2022; Fekkar et al., 2020; Haris et al., 2021; Ibrahim et al., 2011; Kumar & Das, 2024; Lei et al., 2020; Nabil & Yousef, 2020)

Natural corrosion inhibitors have demonstrated substantial efficacy across industrial applications by providing in-situ protection without necessitating operational disruptions. Ongoing research continues to investigate the potential of environmentally friendly inhibitors, aligning with global efforts toward more sustainable industrial practices.

2. METHOD & MATERIALS

2.1 Sample Preparation

In this study, AISI 1020 steel specimens were selected for corrosion testing. The chemical composition of the samples was analysed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy, and the results are presented in Table 1. Meanwhile, Figure 1 summarises the procedure for preparing the corrosion inhibitor.

Table 1. Chemical composition of AISI 1020 steel

Element	Manganese	Carbon	Silicon	Phosphorus	Sulphur	Chromium	Nickel	Copper	Ferrum
Percent (%)	0.56	0.316	0.168	0.022	0.012	0.193	0.081	0.0228	99

Figure 1. The procedure of corrosion inhibitor extraction

2.2 Weight Loss Experimental

The static weight loss method following the ASTM G1-03 standard was employed in this study. This method determines the inhibition efficiency and corrosion rate of AISI 1020 steel. The investigation focused on evaluating waste-derived corrosion inhibitors' influence on steel's corrosion behavior in an acidic environment, specifically in a hydrochloric acid (HCl) solution. The procedure of weight loss experiments is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Weight loss experimental

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Corrosion rate result

The weight loss method was used to compare the different concentrations of 0g(A), 6g(B), 8g(C), and 10g(D) with immersion times (7, 14, and 21 days). Table 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 show data on corrosion rate and corresponding inhibitor efficiency (IE).

Table 2. Data corrosion rate and inhibitors efficiency at several concentrations

Concentration	Corrosion Rate (mm/y) 7 Days	Inhibitor Efficiency (%) 7 Days	Corrosion Rate (mm/y) 14 Days	Inhibitor Efficiency (%) 14 Days	Corrosion Rate (mm/y) 21 Days	Inhibitor Efficiency (%) 21 Days
A	4.4956	0	5.1285	0	5.1275	0
B	0.4088	90.91	0.8269	83.88	0.8958	82.53
C	0.1622	96.39	0.2223	95.67	0.3929	92.34
D	0.0772	98.28	0.1086	97.88	0.2513	95.10

Table 2 presents the corrosion rate and inhibition efficiency of AISI 1020 steel immersed in 1.0 M HCl solution with varying concentrations of eggshell extract over 7 to 21 days. The control sample without any extract (0%) exhibited the highest corrosion rate of 4.4956 mm/year after 7 days. Introducing 6g of eggshell extract significantly reduced the corrosion rate by over 80%. The 10g extract sample showed the most effective inhibition at 7 days, with a corrosion rate of 0.0772 mm/year. A similar trend was observed after 14 days and 21 days, where the 10g extract sample maintained the lowest corrosion rate of 0.1086 mm/year and 0.2513 mm/y compared to other concentrations. These findings suggest that extended immersion leads to increased corrosion due to the aggressive action of chloride ions in HCl, especially when the protective extract is depleted, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Concentration (g) vs corrosion rate (mm/y)

3.2 Inhibitor efficiency result

Figure 4 illustrates the inhibition efficiency of AISI 1020 steel at varying waste extract concentrations. The results show that inhibition efficiency increased with higher waste concentrations, reaching a maximum of 98.28% at 7 days. After 14 days, the highest inhibition efficiency was observed at 10g of extract concentration, with a value of 97.88% and 95.10% in 21 days of immersion. This improvement is attributed to the increased presence of hydroxyl cation elements on the sample surface.

Figure 4. Concentration (g) vs inhibitor efficiency (%)

4. CONCLUSION

This study focused on evaluating the effectiveness of domestic waste extract as a potential natural corrosion inhibitor for AISI 1020 steel in an acidic environment. It concluded that the longer immersion times resulted in a higher corrosion rate than shorter ones. Meanwhile, the longer immersion times affected the value of inhibition efficiency. The highest waste extract concentration in 1.0 M HCl solution demonstrated excellent inhibition efficiency, reaching 98.28% after 7 days, 97.88%, and 95.10% in 21 days, indicating strong corrosion resistance.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like thanks to Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Cawangan Johor, Malaysia, for the approval of the research grant, which enabled us to conduct this study. This study supported by a grant from Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Cawangan Johor, Geran Penyelidikan Bestari Fasa 1/2023, Rujukan 600-TNCPI 5/3/DDN (01) (003/2023).

References

- Arthur, D. E., & Abechi, S. E. (2019). Corrosion inhibition studies of mild steel using *Acalypha chamaedrifolia* leaves extract in hydrochloric acid medium. *SN Applied Sciences*, 1(9). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-1138-4>

- Ayoola, A. A., Babalola, R., Durodola, B. M., Alagbe, E. E., Agboola, O., & Adegbile, E. O. (2022). Corrosion inhibition of A36 mild steel in 0.5 M acid medium using waste citrus limonum peels. *Results in Engineering*, 15, 100490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2022.100490>
- Bijapur, K., Molahalli, V., Shetty, A., Toghan, A., De Padova, P., & Hegde, G. (2023). Recent Trends and Progress in Corrosion Inhibitors and Electrochemical Evaluation. In *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)* (Vol. 13, Issue 18). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app131810107>
- Eddy, N. O., Ibok, U. J., Garg, R., Garg, R., Iqbal, A., Amin, M., Mustafa, F., Egilmez, M., & Galal, A. M. (2022). A Brief Review on Fruit and Vegetable Extracts as Corrosion Inhibitors in Acidic Environments. In *Molecules* (Vol. 27, Issue 9). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27092991>
- Fekkar, G., Yousfi, F., Elmsellem, H., Aiboudi, M., Ramdani, M., Abdel-Rahman, I., Hammouti, B., & Bouyazza, L. (2020). Eco-friendly *Chamaerops humilis* L. fruit extract corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in 1 M HCl. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CORROSION AND SCALE INHIBITION*, 9(2), 446–459. <https://doi.org/10.17675/2305-6894-2020-9-2-4>
- Haris, N. I. N., Sobri, S., Yusof, Y. A., & Kassim, N. K. (2021). Innovative Method for Longer Effective Corrosion Inhibition Time: Controlled Release Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch Hemicellulose Inhibitor Tablet. *MATERIALS*, 14(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma14195657>
- Ibrahim, T. H., Ibrahim, T. H., Chehade, Y., & Zour, M. A. (2011). Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel using Potato Peel Extract in 2M HCl Solution. In *Article in International Journal of Electrochemical Science* (Vol. 6). www.electrochemsci.org
- Kumar, A., & Das, C. (2024). Corrosion inhibition of mild steel by *Praecitrullus fistulosus* (tinda fruit and peel) extracts. *Science of the Total Environment*, 929. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172569>
- Lei, G., Bochuan, T., Wenpo, L., Qingbiao, L., Xingwen, Z., & Ime Bassey, O. (2020). Banana leaves water extracts as inhibitor for X70 steel corrosion in HCl medium. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 327, 114828. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2020.114828>
- Nabil, A.-A., & Yousef, M. (2020). Potential use of eucalyptus leaves as green corrosion inhibitor of steel reinforcement. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 35, 101848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2020.101848>
- Sunardi, S., Ariawan, D., Surojo, E., Prabowo, A. R., Akbar, H. I., Cao, B., & Carvalho, H. (2023). Assessment of eggshell-based material as a green-composite filler: Project milestones and future potential as an engineering material. *Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Materials*, 32(1). <https://doi.org/10.1515/jmbm-2022-0269>